

Novolak Based Adhesives for Metal-Metal Bonding

S. MEERA, PADMA VASUDEVAN* and M. T. CHIPLONKAR

Chemistry Department, I.I.T., New Delhi

Manuscript received 21 May 1976, revised 11 December 1976, accepted 7 January 1977

Aluminium-Aluminium and steel-steel adhesive joints were made with novolak, cured with epichlorohydrin and starch under different conditions. The adhesive strength, both tensile and shear were determined and are discussed as a function of different parameters.

EPOXY resins are perhaps the best known metal-metal adhesives. Structural adhesives^{1a} which are finding increasing importance in metal bonding are the two polymers adhesives that comprise of a thermosetting component along with a thermoplastic component. For example epoxy resins are used with nylon and phenolic resins with polyvinyl acetal, nitrile rubber resins or neoprene rubber. Pure phenolic resins also find a limited use, particularly where high hot strength is needed¹. The type of phenolic resin used is an alkaline resol usually applied in ethanol or acetone solution. Accelerators such as sodium hydroxide or hexamine or mixtures of both are used. The adhesion to metal of unmodified phenolic resins can be increased by adding an epoxy resin and has been used in aircraft industry. Although generally it is the resol form which has been used in formulating adhesives it has been pointed out^{1b} that in novolaks the phenolic groups are still free and by reaction with epichlorohydrin they can be converted into glycidyl polyethers which would be structurally similar to epoxy resins. Thus phenolic novolaks can form a cheaper substitute to bisphenol A. George and Rao² tested the use of epoxy novolak resin cured with aromatic diamines at an elevated temperature in wood, aluminium and wood to aluminium joints. Janis³ discussed the properties of an epoxy novolak adhesive cured with pyromellitic dianhydride, and also of an epoxy novolak modified silicon-phenolic adhesive.

Thus, particularly in the light of the fact established by Narayanamoorthy and coworkers⁴, at the Forest Research Institute in India that phenolic extracts can be obtained from tamarind seeds, tea wastes and species of trees growing in Asiatic mangrove forests and miscellaneous timber, we considered it of interest to experiment with novolak based resins. In the present work we have tested the use of starch as an additive to novolak and compared the adhesive properties with novolak cured with epichlorohydrin and hexa methylene tetramine under the same conditions.

Experimental

Phenol and formalin were taken in the ratio approximately 1 : 1 and were condensed with oxalic

acid by refluxing at 80° for 3 hrs. The novolak was fluid and could be preserved for at least two or three weeks.

Cylindrical butt joints of aluminium-aluminium and steel-steel of various diameters were prepared and their area was determined both by geometry and by actual measurement of the area covered on a graph sheet. The aluminium surface was treated as follows: The specimen was immersed in a 1% solution of sodium hydroxide, and after washing with water was immersed in chromic acid solution, once again washed with water and dried. The steel surface was prepared as follows: The specimen was soaked in methyl ethyl ketone, immersed in oxalic acid solution, washed with water and dried.

A known weight of the novolak was mixed with calculated quantities of formaldehyde and a weighed amount of the curing agent (hexamethylene tetramine, epichlorohydrin, starch). The paste was evenly spread on the two faces of the joint. The ends were clamped together and cured at 70°/120° in an oven, and weighed. The total amount of resin in the joints was known quantitatively and the thickness was thus indirectly controlled. The ratio of the resin to the curing agent was 10 : 1. Also, as was done by Bryant⁵ *et al.* an adhesive layer of known thickness was prepared by incorporating fine copper wires of diameter (1) 0.068 cm, and (2) 0.045 cm. The joints were cured for 24 hrs. After curing the tensile strengths of the joints were measured using a Hounsfield Tensiometer. Some samples were also boiled in water at 100° for 2 hrs, dried in the oven at 70° and tested.

For measuring the tensile-shear strengths, lap joints made up of rectangular aluminium and steel strips were used. The surface treatment and preparation of the joints were done as for the butt joints and after the test the exact area covered was found. The shear strength was also determined on a Hounsfield Tensiometer.

Results and Discussion

The tensile strengths of the butt joints cured with hexamethylene are shown in table 1, those cured with starch in table 2 and the ones cured with

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

epichlorohydrin in table 3. The shear strengths developed in a lap joint with these curing agents in the same order are shown in tables 4, 5, 6. In table 7 the tensile strengths developed in butt joints after incorporation of wire are given.

TABLE 1—TENSILE STRENGTH OF SPECIMENS CURED WITH HEXAMETHYLENE TETRAMINE

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C	Cylinder I : area 1.55 cm ²		Cylinder II : area 6.1 cm ²	
		Amount of Resin (gms)	Tension kg/cm ²	Amount of Resin (gms)	Tension kg/cm ²
1. Al-Al	70	0.2102	5.60	0.8166	5.30
		0.2152	5.16	0.8332	4.91
		0.2282	4.95		
2. Al-Al	120	0.2102	8.01	0.8432	7.50
		0.2108	8.32	0.8612	6.12
		0.2216	6.91		
3. Steel-Steel	70	0.2206	19.30	0.8156	20.50
		0.2212	18.70	0.8212	17.30
		0.2352	17.60		
4. Steel-Steel	120	0.2216	22.00	0.8328	23.20
		0.2218	21.60	0.8312	23.00

TABLE 4—TENSILE SHEAR OF SPECIMENS CURED WITH HEXAMETHYLENE TETRAMINE

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C	Amount of Resin (gms)	Tensile-Shear kg/cm ²
Al-Al	70	0.5018	9.00
		0.5122	8.70
		0.5312	7.90
Al-Al	120	0.5132	10.10
		0.5256	9.50
		0.5532	9.32
Steel-Steel	70	0.5312	12.80
		0.5236	12.10
Steel-Steel	120	0.5202	14.50
		0.5226	13.92

To check for reproducibility several sets of readings have been taken with joints of different areas for a given set of constant curing conditions, regulated thickness and fixed resin curing agent ratio. Comparison with literature values^{1a,7} is difficult as these are for much smaller weights of resin per unit area. Our data indicates that the tensile strength is highly sensitive to the weight of resin used, the general

TABLE 2—TENSILE STRENGTH OF SAMPLES CURED WITH STARCH

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C	Cylinder I : area 1.55 cm ²		Cylinder II : area 6.1 cm ²		Tension after boiling kg/cm ²
		Amount of resin (gms)	Tension kg/cm ²	Amount of resin (gms)	Tension kg/cm ²	
1. Al-Al	70	0.2218	25.4	0.8302	26.5	—
		0.2326	24.5	0.8652	25.1	—
		0.2522	21.0			
2. Al-Al	120	0.2232	30.9	0.8102	32.9	20.0
		0.2358	29.7	0.8592	28.5	19.3
3. Steel-Steel	70	0.2232	59.2	0.8382	61.0	—
		0.2322	57.3	0.8812	58.3	—
4. Steel-Steel	120	0.2106	71.0	0.8552	73.2	54.6
		0.2252	68.6	0.9132	66.1	52.6

TABLE 3—TENSILE STRENGTH OF SPECIMENS CURED WITH EPICHLOROHYDRIN

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C	Cylinder I : area 1.55 cm ²		Cylinder II : area 6.1 cm ²		Tension after boiling kg/cm ²
		Amount of resin (gms)	Tension kg/cm ²	Amount of resin (gms)	Tension kg/cm ²	
1. Al-Al	70	0.2056	36.1	0.8222	37.8	
		0.2122	33.5	0.8912	33.2	
		0.2282	29.0			
2. Al-Al	120	0.2106	71.0	0.8312	70.1	65.3
		0.2182	63.3	0.9232	61.0	62.7
		0.2204	62.3			
3. Steel-Steel	70	0.2134	59.8	0.8856	59.5	
		0.2136	57.6	0.9232	55.3	
		0.2202	52.3			
4. Steel-Steel	120	0.2252	121.2	0.8102	116.2	116.7
		0.2302	118.3	0.9152	109.3	112.6
		0.2528	111.3			

TABLE 5—TENSILE-SHEAR OF SPECIMENS CURED WITH STARCH

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C	Amount of Resin (gms)	Shear kg/cm ²	Shear on boiling kg/cm ²
Al-Al	70	0.5210	13.60	
		0.5286	13.06	
Al-Al	120	0.5018	15.20	11.3
		0.5312	14.50	9.8
		0.5322	14.10	
Steel-Steel	70	0.5032	21.60	
		0.5102	20.30	
		0.5236	19.60	
Steel-Steel	120	0.5212	23.40	20.5
		0.5364	22.40	19.6
		0.5432	21.10	

TABLE 6—TENSILE-SHEAR OF SPECIMENS CURED WITH EPICHLOROHYDRIN

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C	Amount of Resin (gms)	Shear kg/cm ²	Shear after boiling kg/cm ²
Al-Al	70	0.5232	11.30	
		0.5246	10.93	
		0.5306	10.52	
Al-Al	120	0.5102	25.20	21.0
		0.5252	24.50	20.2
		0.5396	23.50	
Steel-Steel	70	0.5202	33.60	30.6
		0.5216	32.80	29.6
		0.5356	32.10	

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF INCORPORATION OF WIRE ON TENSILE STRENGTH

Type of Joints	Curing Temp. °C and agent	Thickness cm	Tension kg/cm ²
Al-Al	120	0.045	27.1
		0.068	26.5
	Starch	0.068	24.9
Steel-Steel	120	0.045	23.2
		0.068	62.5
	Starch	0.068	61.0
Al-Al	120	0.045	56.9
		0.068	55.4
	epichlorohydrin	0.045	64.3
Steel-Steel	120	0.045	63.1
		0.068	60.5
	epichlorohydrin	0.045	59.3
Steel-Steel	120	0.045	105.5
		0.068	102.2
	epichlorohydrin	0.068	99.9
			98.3

trend being an increase in strength with decrease of the weight. The plot of tensile strength versus weight of the resin is linear, but the experimental range over which the weight is varied is too small to give any conclusive results. It is seen that for a given curing agent the values for steel-steel joints are higher than for aluminium-aluminium joints. In all cases better strength was obtained on curing at 120° as compared to that at 70°. Although epichlorohydrin gave a stronger bond than starch cured at 120°, the strength with starch was as good as that for epichlorohydrin if the temperature of curing was 70°. The effect of thickness is also demonstrated by the values obtained for wire incorporated joints. However, unlike Bryant *et al.*, we found that the incorporation of wire reduced the strength and hence comparison could not be made with values obtained without these inclusions.

The tests with the help of lap joints show similar trends except that the values are lower by nearly an order of magnitude. Once again the strength is highly sensitive to thickness. On boiling with water there is no loss in the strength of joints cured with epichlorohydrin while the ones cured with starch lose some strength.

Conclusion

Novolaks can be used to give strong metal-metal adhesive bonds. Starch compares with epichlorohydrin in curing at low temperatures.

Acknowledgement

The work formed a part of the post-graduate project submitted by S.M. We thank the Heads of the Departments of Chemistry and Applied Mechanics for the facilities and Mr. S. K. Mittal in helping with the tensile measurements.

References

- 1a. R. HOUWINK and G. SALOMON, "Adhesion and Adhesives", Vol. I, Elsevier Publishing Company, 1967, p. 217.
- b. R. HOUWINK and G. SALOMON, "Adhesion and Adhesives", Vol. I, Elsevier Publishing Company, 1967, p. 273.
2. J. GEROGE and P. RAMACHANDRA RAO, *Paint India*, 1960, 10, 20.
3. E. C. JANIS, ASTM Symposium on adhesion and adhesives, San Francisco, Oct. 1951.
4. D. NARAYANAMURTHY, D. R. RAMACHANDRA RAO and R. RAM, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1958, 6 (4), 43.
5. R. W. BRYANT, *Nature*, 1964, 202, 1087.